

PSYCHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF ABILITIES

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Annotation: This article examines the psychological structure of abilities. An analysis of leading theoretical concepts is given and the main methodological guidelines that contribute to the targeted identification, study and development of abilities are revealed.

Key words: structure of abilities, components, abilities of the individual.

Pri obraschenii k sovremennym issledovaniyam it is necessary to under-cherknut, chto novye podkhody ne protivorechat vajnomu pozheniyu otechestvennoy teorii, kotoroe zaklyuchaetsya v primenenii principle obshchego, osobennogo i edinichnogo k analizu kobnostey. The use of the ego (T.I. Artemeva) allows you to see the psychological structure of abilities, which includes:

— the general component, the social structure and the social structure of the society;

- osobenny, spetsialnyy component, obuslovlennyy sp-tsficheskimi chertami togo ili inogo screw deyatelnosti;

— edinichnyy, individual component, raskryvayushchiy ka-chestvennoe svoeobrazie kobnostey dannogo individa.

Obraschayas k voprosam sootnoshenia sotsialnogo i individual-nogo v hulovecheskikh kobnostyakh, sleduet otmetit znachitelnyy klakad v etu problemu nauchnykh trudov K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskoi. Development idea S.L. Rubinstein and A.N. Leonteva, ona podcherkivaet, chto individ kak obshchestvennoe sushchestvo lish v obshchest-ve i posredstvom obshchestva mojet razvivat i sovershenstvovat svoi svoi svetnosti. Poetomu razvitie individualnykh kobnostey vklyuchaet svoim nepremennym usloviem prisvoenie produktov kul-tury, vyrabotannyx obshchestvom. However, human culture, which has reached the level of cultural development, affects the development of the individual's abilities, and does not directly and indirectly determine that level, just as the development of the ability is determined only by the available products of human culture, and before that, all the actions of the individual are prisvoeniyyu. Priche sam chelovek and etom procese ne passiven, chto nelzya upuskat iz vidu pri ana-lize ego formostey. Bessporno i to, chto "psychicheskaya deyatelnost, ne proizvodya

zneznogo dlya oshchestva product, doljna imet svoy, oblettvoryayushchi ee result, iz kotorogo mother draws dal-neysuyu activity"¹ In this regard, the ability itself can be considered as an active principle, as "activity in a not yet developed form."

The author explores under what conditions activity actually develops an individual's abilities. Depending on the way of consuming products of human culture, an individual can:

a) to develop within the framework of those achievements that are recorded in cultural objects, and then it is more correct to talk not about abilities, but about knowledge, abilities and skills, considering the development process as the reproduction by an individual of what is already available in the general fund of cultural values;

b) develop your abilities as such, as a result of which something new is added to what is recorded in a given period of time. In this case, we can talk about abilities in the true understanding of their meaning as creativity - going beyond the boundaries of a given type of activity. This is designated by the author as the principle of concreteness and individuality in the analysis of abilities.

Returning to the initial principles that the human individual has certain potential properties and mental characteristics, but the latter can arise, be realized and develop only under certain social conditions, Abulkhanova-Slavskaya emphasizes that their influence does not at all go in the direction of equalizing individuals, their standardization. The above approaches take the formulation of the problem of developing abilities beyond the traditional limits of their connection only with a special type of activity, and make it possible to consider a broader (than just activity) set of prerequisites for individual abilities. At the same time, mental activity is considered as a "regulator of life activity" of a given, specific individual, and differences in mental characteristics and abilities are explained not only by the laws of the psyche itself, but also by the place the individual occupies in society.

To summarize all of the above, it can be argued that familiarity with leading theoretical concepts is undoubtedly useful both for teachers and for students - future teachers of any specialty (including music). It convinces them that the problem of abilities is of a universal nature, that special abilities should be considered as part of the whole, that the study of the psychological mechanism of abilities, the general laws of their formation provides the main guidelines for their

¹ Абульханова-Славская К. А. Некоторые особенности эстетического переживания // Взаимосвязь методологической и методической подготовки учителя музыки. — М., 1994. стр 22

development in specific types of activities, and finally allows us to develop the basic methodological settings that promote targeted identification, study and development of abilities.

Abilities are complex formations in which natural inclinations, individual psychological characteristics of a person and the social component interact - socially developed knowledge and methods of action. All these components are fused into ability only in appropriate activity and as a result of communication.

Abilities manifest themselves and develop in conditions of active and adequate activity. At the same time, the relationship between abilities and knowledge, abilities, skills is important: abilities are, on the one hand, prerequisites for mastering knowledge, abilities, skills and, on the other hand, they develop themselves in the process of this mastery.

Abilities are not only the result of a person's own activities - they are also formed as a result of social influence - communication, training, education. At the same time, it is necessary to keep in mind that abilities cannot simply be implanted from the outside - each person has his own internal conditions for their functioning, which must be taken into account in his work. One cannot ignore the active principle in a person, his own activity, when mental activity becomes the regulator of the entire life activity of the individual.

Each activity places certain demands on both special and general abilities. Therefore, it is not enough to develop a personality narrowly professionally - only its comprehensive development will ensure the identification and formation of both general and special abilities in their unity. Hence the two-sided tasks of taking into account the specifics of the profession and adjusting general and special development.

Abilities are not an isolated manifestation of personality; they are in organic unity with other qualities in the holistic makeup of mental life. On the other hand, each individual ability is a complex of different properties connected by complex interactions. This requires the teacher to understand their role in the "ensemble", and, first of all, to pay close attention to the interests and inclinations of the person. Paying attention to inclinations and determining the abilities behind them, one must not lose sight of the formation of other internal prerequisites for the development of abilities - such characterological traits as determination and organization, efficiency and self-demandingness.

Theoretical analysis of abilities and pedagogical practice bring to the fore the problem of differences in the mental activity of people; these differences are associated not only with physiological characteristics, but also with different

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ways of their life. At the same time, qualitative differences in abilities lead to different ways of performing the same activity and provide opportunities for “compensation of abilities.” Thus, successful creative performance of activities can be achieved in different ways. This presupposes an individual approach to the development of each person.

Abilities as general qualities of a person are part of its structure and are closely related to the character, will, and goals of a person. Therefore, it is possible to understand, and therefore develop, abilities only in connection with the study of the personality as a whole. This confronts the teacher with the task of bridging the gap between abilities and other human properties. On the other hand, the main goal of abilities is precisely the formation of the student’s personality, including the development of such qualities and properties that are necessary for various types of activities and can even become decisive in his entire life. This goal opens up prospects for the teacher’s personal and creative influence on the student and turns education into “the process of purposefully creating an atmosphere of life in which ... all the musical and, more broadly, spiritual values accumulated by humanity are realized.”

Following this path is of particular importance for teachers - it raises their activities to a higher methodological level, which allows them to see the entire development process as a whole. At the same time, issues of practical pedagogy are closely linked with philosophical, aesthetic, psychological and pedagogical problems.

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